

The Historical Overview on Ambagad Fort in Bhandara District

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Abstract

Forts are witnesses of history, they are symbols of ancient civilizations. The forts were not only for the residence of the king, but also for the protection of the subjects, and their usefulness was to keep the entire subject in check. Even today, many forts stand witnessing the history. Even after so many years, these forts still look strong. The skill and hard work required to build the fort can be seen from this building. In the present paper, Ambagad fort located in Bhandara district has been analyzed and a historical review has been done.

Keywords : Ambagad, Vandurg, Historical, Overview

Introduction

The Satpuda mountain ranges are spread from east to west along the northern border of Vidarbha. To the south of this range in Vidarbha lies Bhandara district. The southern hills of the Satpura range passing through Bhandara district are known as Ambagad hills. In this hill there is Ambagad forest fort called Ambagad Vandurg. This forest fort is located in Ambagad village in Tumsar tehsil of Bhandara district. Historical analysis of this fort has been done in this paper.

Objectives

The main objective of this study is to describe the historical importance of the forest fort of Ambagad in its present situation.

Data Source & Methodology

The analysis of the presented paper is mainly based on secondary sources. This information is based on daily current papers, published books, previously published research papers, articles, and information available on internet. It is also based on the experience after actually visiting this fort. Comprehension of the information collected and presented in one's own words.

Location of Ambagad Fort (Vandurg)

Ambagadh is a forest fort in the north of Bhandara district. Latitudinal position of this fort is 21° 26' 48" North and Longitudinal position 79° 40' 46" East. The height of this fort is 534 meters above sea level. Tourists and hikers find the fort easy to climb.

Transport Accessibility and Accommodation Facility

It is convenient to go to Ambagad from Bhandara. The route from Bhandara goes through Tumsar. After heading towards Gobarwahi after Tumsar tehsil, one can go to Ambagad from Mitewani. Also, one can reach Ambagad from Nagpur via Ramtek to Kandri and from there via Gaymukh. As Bhandara is the main place of the district, good private hotels and government accommodation are available in the vicinity of the railway station and bus station. There is no accommodation facility available for tourists in Ambagad area.

The Historical Overview

In 1700 AD, there is a mention of the construction of the Ambagad fort by Bakhtabuland Shah, a Sardar of Rajkhan Pathan of Shivani. It is a very steep climb and this fort is a very strong construction on the Satapuda mountain range and is still standing as a testimony of its past glory. Similarly, many characteristics of Gond rule are seen in this Ambagad Vandurga. The total area of this fort is 47045 square meters and the length of this fort is about 1802 feet in the north and 131 feet in the south. It is also 279 feet to the east and 262 feet to the west. At the eastern foothills of Ambagad there is a temple of Hanuman. There is a way to go to the fort from near this temple. This road leading to the fort is on the east side of the fort and the steps along this route are newly constructed. It takes twenty to twenty five minutes to reach the fort's Mahadwara. The bastions near this entrance are built of lime and brick. On entering through the door, the first thing you see is the guards' quarters. There is a tower at the top and a view of the fort's surroundings. There are gun emplacements on the bastions within the fortifications. The heights of these are also in a dilapidated condition. The shape of the fort is oblong and manageable. Three to four stories are built on the middle plateau. After walking from here, this road leads to the western end of the fort. It takes around an hour and a half to walk around the entire fort. While visiting the fort, one can see the ruins of small palaces, beautiful stone umbrellas and baths, horse stables, ambarkhana, water tanks. Also, there is a Muslim shrine called Bandzira near the fort, and around the road leading here, one can see the magnificent ponds and Bagheda reservoir. Also the dense forest around the fort is visible. Ambagad fort has a basement. There are steps to get down in this and this place is called Aadhaar Kothdi. To the south of the basement is a living room and the basement has two grand rooms. They have beautiful carved arches. There is a small window in this basement through which air and sunlight come in and there is a very pungent smell. Ambagad Fort is a unique example of Gond architecture and Raghuji Bhosale established his rule over this area in 1740 AD. The Bhosale rulers

of Nagpur used this fort as a prison to keep criminals. Criminals were killed by drinking poisonous water from the well in this fort. The British took over this fort around 1892 and the maintenance and repair of this fort was entrusted to the famous Malgujar Shri Ganpatrao Pandey. Manbhatta Upadhyay, who fought against the British in the battle of Sitabardi in 1817, was kept in this fort. Also Dharmaji Bhosle was also kept in this fort and he died by drinking the polluted air and poisonous well water. There are many legends about this fort. Koshti Kavadu Patel here was arrested for witchcraft and imprisoned in the basement of this fort. He also died after drinking the poisonous water of the well there. He was later buried on a hill near the settlement at the base of the fort. His grave is called the God of Ambagadh by the local people and worshipers and vows are found at his grave.

Present Situation of Ambagad

As the ramparts of Ambagad fort have collapsed in many places, it is not possible to take a ferry from the ramparts. Also the tower on the left is in a state of collapse. Due to lack of cleaning and proper maintenance, large trees have grown on this fort and the ruins of the fort are dilapidated at many places. For the development and conservation of Ambagad Forest Fort, it is necessary to repair and maintain the construction on the fort properly. Also, for the development of tourism, it is necessary to develop transport system, food system and drinking water system etc. in the fort. Thus, the number of tourists will increase and the information about the importance and history of this fort will reach the masses.

References

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